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INTRODUCTION

Marine Annelida represent an interesting source of inspiration for robotics. They can undergo morphological changes, involving dramatic modifications of their shape and protrusion of parts of their bodies, as a response to environmental stimuli and as part of their burrowing behavior and feeding strategy.

In this regard, the MAPWORMS project aims to develop soft shape-morphing robots inspired by marine Annelida, capable to react to environmental cues by relying on actuation units based on different smart materials and assembled in a smart and modular architecture.

Among marine Annelida, two main categories of potential model organisms have been identified:

- **Unsegmented Annelida (Sipuncula, Echiura);**
- **Annelida with eversible, armed pharynx (Phyllodocida, Eunicida).**

Annelida from the former category are able to adapt to the surrounding environment by shape-morphing. Indeed, while in the majority of Annelida the metameric structure limits the extent of morphological changes to a part of their body, segmentation is completely absent in the selected ones (i.e., Sipuncula and Echiura), where a single water-filled cavity spans the whole body and morphological changes involve the entire organism. Moreover, these unsegmented worms have an eversible introvert which, together with the simple body structure, makes them particularly interesting for this project.

Regarding the latter category, the presence of hard structures within the pharynx and its eversion mechanism – finely tuned to avoid damages to soft tissues – suggests that the study of the pharynx eversion might give clues about how to safely integrate a rigid instrument into a soft robot, without damaging the robot itself nor the surroundings.

To fully understand the dynamic shape-morphing strategy of Sipuncula and Echiura worms and the eversion mechanism of the Phyllodocida and Eunicida pharynx, a mathematical model is required. Thus, we are developing a model for the kinematics of the outer body wall of the worms, seen as a thin elastic shell endowed by actively stretchable fibers. The same modelling approach is exploited for both worm categories, setting different parameters obtained through their characterization. Thus, the performances and features of the selected worms have to be deeply analyzed for setting proper model parameters as well as for validating the final model results.

In this regard, some preliminary results have been already available in the Consortium thanks to a previous collaboration between SSSA and CoNISMa, published in Filogna et al (2020). In particular, a marker-less optical tracking strategy was used to study the protrusion capabilities of *Phascolosoma stephensoni* (i.e., a species of Sipuncula). The obtained results demonstrated that these worms can reach lengths up to three times their initial ones after protrusion in sea water (i.e., outside from the burrow). Moreover, they are able to elongate their introvert inside agar-based hydrogel and to navigate easily inside it, thus exerting forces up to 3 N and stresses of some tens of kPa, depending on the body size.

Starting from these preliminary results, a more accurate characterization of the worm parameters for modelling is pursued in the MAPWORMS project, on both the selected categories. During these months of the project, we mainly focused on the development of the required experimental set-ups for extracting worm data. In particular, images and videos of the worms moving in different media

are acquired by a camera equipped with a 10 mm scale and analyzed to evaluate sizes of different external body parts and movement speeds. For the internal characterization of the worms, micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) is used, as this technology has the ability to visualise the internal and external morphology in three dimensions. Furthermore, quantitative data are derived by the 3D analysis performed in the micro-CT datasets, which allow the characterization of several parameters for modelling. Finally, a proper experimental set-up is integrated into an Instron Testing Machine to characterize the properties of the media used in the aquaria with worms, in order to set proper environmental parameters into the model and to allow for indirect worm force measurements.

A number of preliminary data have been acquired focusing mainly on the first category of worms (i.e., on unsegmented Annelida, and, in particular, on Sipuncula) due to their ease of collection and manipulation. We also started to analyze the pharynx movements in the second group that will be also explored in more detail during the next months. All these preliminary results are reported in the present Deliverable D2.2 - *First set of parameters for modelling*. The dataset will be completed during the next months and reported in the Deliverable D2.4 - *Annelida performance final characterization* due at month M33. This complete dataset will allow to set and validate the the final worm models.

ANATOMY AND MORPHOLOGY OF THE SELECTED WORMS

1. UNSEGMENTED ANNELIDA (SIPUNCULA, ECHIURA)

Annelida with unsegmented bodies are able to adapt to the surrounding environment by shape-morphing strategies which turn out particularly interesting for the development of new worm-inspired robots. In particular, unlike Echiura, Sipuncula can be easily collected and manipulated. Thus, during these months of the project, the characterization was mainly focused on Sipuncula.

The body of Sipuncula consists of a single chamber (named coelomic cavity) with a body wall composed of muscular and connective tissues organized in layers, filled with a water-based liquid (i.e., coelomic fluid). It can be broadly divided into an anterior (introvert) and a posterior (trunk) portion characterized by different bio-mechanic features (Fig. 1) (Pancucci-Papadopoulou et al., 1999).

Figure 1. *Phascolosoma stephensoni* Stephen, 1942, a typical representative of the sipunculan body plan.

During eversion and protrusion movements, the trunk remains relatively unchanged, while the introvert is the part of the worm that actually undergoes morphological changes and moves. More specifically, the introvert is pulled inside the posterior part of the body by the retractor muscles, which are attached on one end to the distal extremity of the introvert, near the mouth of the worm, and on the other end to the posterior part of the trunk (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. Volume rendering of A) a fully extended and B) a contracted *Phascolosoma stephensoni* acquired using micro-CT technology. C-D) Surface rendering of the retractor muscles of the *Phascolosoma stephensoni* specimen in C) fully extended and D) contracted position (countour mesh generated by DragonFly ORS software).

The retracted introvert can be protruded outside by contracting the circular muscles in its elastic body wall, thus inducing an elongation by working on the inner incompressible fluid in the coelomic cavity, which acts as a hydro-skeleton (Fig. 3). The longitudinal muscles have a less pronounced role in Sipuncula than in regular Annelida. Indeed, in regular Annelida the contraction of longitudinal muscles shortens and thickens some body segments, allowing the chaetae to grip on the external surface. It happens while the contraction of the circular muscles squeezes and elongates other body segments, thus enabling the peristaltic movement of the worm. On the contrary, Sipuncula do not have a segmented body, and peristaltic movements are very limited. Nevertheless, longitudinal muscles in Sipuncula allow for a differential thickening and stiffening of parts of the trunk and the introvert, thus playing an important role, for example, to get a grip on the sediment and to push the body forward, or to get stuck into crevices, as well as during bending movements.

Figure 3. Cross-section images of longitudinal and circular muscles of the *Phascolosoma stephensoni* specimen in A) fully expanded and B) contracted position.

2. ANNELIDA WITH EVERISIBLE, ARMED PHARYNX (PHYLLODOCIDA, EUNICIDA).

Errant polychaetes (generally split in the two orders Phyllodocida and Eunicida) are characterized by a typical annelidan anatomy, with an elongated, segmented body. Each segment is filled by the coelomic fluid and separated by the other segment by septa, allowing for the independent movement of each segment. The movement of errant polychaetes is basically a slightly modified version of the typical peristaltic movement widespread in annelids and, as such, not particularly interesting for this project. However, several groups of errant annelids are characterized by the presence of an eversible, armed pharynx, which is used to process large food items (either vegetal or animal). Eversible pharynxes are present in the majority of the families belonging to the order Phyllodocida, and in all the families belonging to the order Eunicida; in the majority of these cases pharynxes are armed with hard jaw pieces, whose structure is based on collagen, but it is often reinforced by a mineralized layer (Fig. 4) (Rouse & Pleijel, 2001). The order Eunicida is characterized by a pharyngeal bulb that does not change the orientation during the protrusion, and by a complex system of jaw pieces, typically including a lower jaw piece (also known as *labium*), several mineralized pieces forming the upper jaw (known as maxillary teeth or *maxillae*), and a posterior elongated, hard structure, where the muscles operating the pharyngeal bulb are inserted, known as carriers. Members of the order Eunicida are typically predators or scavengers, and the numerous jaw pieces are used to both capture preys, and to mince them in smaller pieces.

Figure 4. *Glycera alba* (O. F. Müller, 1776) with partially everted pharynx, showing in transparency the jaws.

Pharyngeal structures of Phyllodocida show a more limited variation in the structure of jaws, but a higher variability in the length of the pharynx and its eversion. Phyllodocida typically have paired jaws (either two or four), even if several groups completely lack hard pharyngeal structures (e.g., the family Phyllodocidae) or just have some small, unpaired teeth (e.g. the families Syllidae and Pilargidae). In Phyllodocida, jaw pieces are usually not as mineralized as in Eunicida, and typically occur in two shapes, i.e., serrated plates with several teeth (e.g. the suborder Aphroditiformia or the family Nereididae), or slightly curved, smooth structures with an acute tip, which might be associated with venom glands (e.g. the families Chrysopetalidae and Glyceridae). The length of the eversible pharynx is instead rather variable, and in some groups it can be as long as 1/3 – 1/4 of the entire body length. While in some groups (as the Aphroditiformia) the pharynx does not change orientation during the protrusion, in several groups it is at least partially everted, with the terminal part (including the jaws) maintaining the same orientation throughout the eversion process.

In this study, Glyceridae specimens were selected as representatives of Phyllodocida order. The pharynx of Glycerids is of remarkable length. The protruded part of the pharynx is the buccal tube which is often only partially inverted (Fig 5); however, on complete protrusion, the jaws are exposed (Dales, 1962).

Figure 5. Volume rendering of unstained A, B) *Glycera tridactyla* Schmarda, 1861 and C) *Glycera alba* (O.F. Müller, 1776) in three different configurations. White arrow indicates the pharynx, while the dashed arrow indicates the jaws.

Several muscles are important during eversion and protrusion movements. The contraction of the circular muscles leads to the contraction of buccal tube longitudinal muscles resulting in its retraction (Fig 6). Details about the eversion and protrusion movements of the proboscis can be found in Dales (1962).

Figure 6. Pharyngeal anatomy of *Glycera tridactyla*. Jaws are also visualised as colour-coded structure thickness image.

MATHEMATICAL MODELLING OF WORMS

We model the eversion behavior of the selected species by means of a 2D non-local, non-standard shell model with tunable stretches in given directions.

We approximate the analyzed part of the body worms in the rest configuration as a cylinder with initial radius R_0 and height H_0 (Fig. 7). The parallels and meridians of this cylinder correspond to the circular and longitudinal muscle fibers of the biological counterpart; the intrinsic strain of the cylinder along these directions can then be controlled to mimick the muscle contraction in the muscle body wall of the worms. In fact, a change in the intrinsic strain at a fiber increases the internal energy of the system, which is no longer at an optimal configuration. Upon a numerical optimization procedure, the final configuration of the system changes so that the strain along that fiber is closer to the imposed intrinsic one, so that the tubular structure appears to have contracted along that fiber.

By assuming axisymmetry of deformations during the eversion and retraction phases, we can consider only a subset of the possible deformations that the cylinder could undergo, which can be described analytically, exploiting tools of differential geometry of surfaces, and then solved numerically. In particular, axisymmetry allows us to compute the overall energy associated to muscle fibers as the sum of a single one times their number, greatly simplifying computations.

Figure 7. Schematics of the hypothesis of axisymmetric deformations of the worm body wall. The map χ_0 expresses the initial configuration of the introvert, while χ denotes a generic deformed configuration.

During these months, a preliminary model of the former category (i.e., unsegmented Annelida: Sipuncula, Echiura) was developed. However, a deep characterization of the worms is required to extend this preliminary model to cover more accurate geometries for the worm's introvert. The same approach will be exploited also for the second category (i.e., Annelida with an eversible, armed pharynx, Phyllodocida, Eunicida). The aim is to "reverse-engineer" the role of the different muscles in enforcing the shapes observed in living organisms and in controlling their motility.

The final dataset of the characterization of worms will be reported in the Deliverable D2.4 - *Annelida performance final characterization* (due at month M33) and will allow for finalizing the setting of the worm models as well as the validation of the final results of simulations.

1. PRELIMINARY MODEL FOR UNSEGMENTED ANNELIDA (SIPUNCULA, ECHIURA)

For the selected unsegmented Annelida (Sipuncula, Echiura), the loading of the introvert in the retraction phase, which is carried out by retractor muscles in the biological system, is reproduced in the model by means of a simple axial force, acting as a pulley on the upper end of the cylinder. During the eversion phase, we reproduced the hydroskeleton mechanism observed in the worm: upon contraction of the circular muscle fibers (parallels in the model), the incompressibility of the inner fluid (imposed through a constraint in the model) forces a motion of the fluid towards the retracted introvert, which is thus forced to unfold.

In our model, we account for the incompressible coelomic fluid by imposing that the inner volume of the structure remains constant. The hydroskeleton mechanism is then reproduced by a volume conservation law: the contraction of a parallel would induce a volume reduction, which is compensated by the unfolding of the retracted portion of the introvert.

In particular, the sketch reported in Fig. 8 illustrates the workflow of the described model in a schematic cylindrical geometry for the introvert. The basic mechanism adopted is the following: retraction is achieved by the action of retractor muscles, mimicked by an applied axial force; protrusion is then caused by circular muscles, the action of which is reproduced by the active control of the stretches along the parallels of the initial cylinder.

In the future, the model will be extended to cover geometries that approximate more accurately the worm's introvert.

Figure 8. Schematics of the workflow of the model: an axial force causes the retraction of the introvert, obtaining an everted shape; the active control of stretches along parallels together with force release allows the structure to protrude back.

FIRST SET OF PARAMETERS FOR MODELING

This chapter describes the experimental set-ups developed to measure the worm data required for modelling. In particular, the chapter is divided into three main sections:

- *Standardised measurements on external anatomy and movement* – This section reports the experimental set-up exploited for the evaluation of the sizes of different body parts and speed movements of worms. In particular, image and video analysis of worms moving in specific aquaria with different media was carried out. Preliminary data acquired on Sipuncula are also reported.
- *Reconstruction of internal anatomy and standardised measurements on anatomical elements involved in the movement* (Section) – This section describes the method for the characterization of the internal anatomy of worms by microCT technology. In this case, preliminary data measured on Sipuncula and Phyllodocida specimens are reported.
- *Measurement of equivalent viscosity* – This section reports the experimental set-up used for the characterization of the different types of media used in the aquaria with worms. These measurements allow for an indirect evaluation of worm forces, as well as for a proper setting of the environmental conditions during simulations.

In the next months, these experimental set-ups will be exploited for finalizing the characterization of the different types of worms selected as sources of bioinspiration in the project, thus achieving the final dataset for model setting and validation.

STANDARDISED MEASUREMENTS ON EXTERNAL ANATOMY AND MOVEMENT

Standardised measurements of the external anatomy were performed on live individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni* in narrow aquaria (thickness \ll width/height) filled with seawater using videos obtained with a Canon EOS 90D camera equipped with a 10 mm scale (Fig. 9).

Figure 9. Experimental video set-up used for the characterization of worms.

Three different 10x10 cm² aquaria with a width of 4 mm, 7 mm, and 10 mm are used during characterization tests on the base of the worm dimensions. These narrow design of the aquaria aims at imposing planar movements on worms, thus simplifying the extraction of the required data by the analysis of 2D images.

In particular, frames from videos were analysed with the software ImageJ (Schneider et al., 2012) to obtain accurate measurements of the length and radius of the animals. Measurements regarding length and radius of the worms were obtained on live animals in seawater, using frames where the worms were completely contracted and completely extended. With this setting we obtained the following measurements (see also Figs. 10):

- Initial rest length of the worm as a whole: total length of the worm in contracted state, with introvert almost completely retracted ($TL1 = TrL1 + InL1$, where $TL1$ is the initial total length of the worm, $TrL1$ is the initial length of the trunk and $InL1$ is the initial length of the introvert).
- Initial rest length of the worm introvert: length of the retracted introvert ($InL1$).
- Initial radius of the worm trunk: radius of the trunk in the completely contracted worm ($W1$).
- Initial radius of the worm introvert: radius of the introvert in contracted state ($W2$).
- Final length of the worm as a whole: total length of the completely extended worm ($TL2 = TrL2 + InL2$, where $TL2$ is the final total length of the worm, $TrL2$ is the final length of the trunk and $InL2$ is the final length of the introvert).
- Final length of the worm introvert: length of the completely extended introvert ($InL2$).
- Final radius of the worm trunk: radius of the trunk in the completely extended worm ($W3$).
- Final radius of the worm introvert: radius of the introvert in the completely extended worm, measured at the basis ($W4$), at the tip ($W7$), and in two intermediate positions ($W5$, $W6$).

Size measurements were repeatedly performed on five different individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni*, which were subsequently used to obtain speed estimates of the introvert movement. The biometric measurements obtained for the five selected individuals of *P. stephensoni* are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Biometric measurements ([mm], mean \pm standard deviation) obtained on five individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni*.

		Worm 1	Worm 2	Worm 3	Worm 4	Worm 5
Contracted	TL1	5.68 \pm 0.09	3.90 \pm 0.07	5.28 \pm 0.06	5.3 \pm 0.23	6.02 \pm 0.06
	InL1	1.27 \pm 0.10	0.58 \pm 0.05	1.14 \pm 0.03	0.43 \pm 0.08	1.37 \pm 0.09
	W1	1.52 \pm 0.04	0.93 \pm 0.05	2 \pm 0.03	1.13 \pm 0.07	1.41 \pm 0.01
	W2	1.10 \pm 0.05	0.49 \pm 0.05	1.19 \pm 0.0	0.88 \pm 0.02	1.18 \pm 0.09
Extended	TL2	15.13 \pm 0.31	9.63 \pm 0.66	10.56 \pm 0.40	10.81 \pm 0.99	18.56 \pm 0.17
	InL2	9.54 \pm 0.26	5.95 \pm 0.55	7.18 \pm 0.90	6.51 \pm 0.18	12.39 \pm 0.62
	W3	1.03 \pm 0.05	0.77 \pm 0.04	1.56 \pm 0.10	0.94 \pm 0.02	1.04 \pm 0.07
	W4	0.86 \pm 0.09	0.46 \pm 0.01	1.16 \pm 0.14	0.77 \pm 0.02	0.83 \pm 0.05
	W5	0.76 \pm 0.05	0.43 \pm 0.04	0.84 \pm 0.01	0.58 \pm 0.06	0.57 \pm 0.05
	W6	0.65 \pm 0.04	0.34 \pm 0.02	0.72 \pm 0.07	0.55 \pm 0.06	0.50 \pm 0.08
	W7	0.37 \pm 0.03	0.26 \pm 0.03	0.49 \pm 0.05	0.40 \pm 0.03	0.43 \pm 0.10

Figure 10. A-B) Length measurements obtained on retracted and extended individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni*. C-D) Width measurements obtained on contracted and extended individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni*.

After the characterization of the length and radius of the worms, additional tests were carried out to evaluate the speed of worms when moving in the aquaria filled with 0.5% agarose gel (Fig. 11). The digging behaviour of the worm in the filled aquaria was filmed using the same camera and settings employed for observations in seawater (Fig. 9), and the speed of the protrusion and retraction of the introvert was measured using the software ImageJ on subsequent frames taken at a known time. For each worm in each experimental condition at least five different speed estimates were obtained. We observed that during the digging behaviour the trunk was passively following the introvert, and in the majority of cases did not actively contribute to the movement; for this reason, we only characterized the movement of the introvert.

Figure 11. Experimental setting used for the measurement of the protrusion and retraction speed of *Phascolosoma stephensoni* in a 0.5% agarose gel.

Protrusion speed showed variations with the aquarium size. In the 4-mm aquarium, the average protrusion speed was 0.76 ± 0.09 mm/s, in the 7-mm aquarium, it was 1.13 ± 0.39 mm/s, and in the 10-mm aquarium it was 0.44 ± 0.06 mm/s (Table 2). In all experimental conditions, protrusion speed did not show a clear relationship with the size of the worm. Even if in the smallest aquarium (blue line) the speed showed a weak negative linear relationship with size, this effect could be due to the physical constraint represented by the aquarium walls in the case of the larger worms (Fig. 12).

Figure 12. Relationship between worm size and protrusion speed measured in the three experimental aquaria.

Retraction speed showed a similar pattern of variation with the aquarium size. In this case, the average retraction speed in the 4-mm aquarium was 0.38 ± 0.18 mm/s, the average retraction speed in the 7-mm aquarium was 1.79 ± 0.82 mm/s, and the average retraction speed in the 10-mm aquarium was 0.40 ± 0.17 mm/s (Table 2). Retraction speed did not show any particular relationship with size, even if in the 4-mm aquarium a weak positive linear relationship between size and retraction speed can be noticed (Fig. 13). In any case, both protrusion and retraction speeds were distinctly higher in the 7-mm aquarium.

Table 2. Protrusion and retraction speed ([mm/s], mean \pm standard deviation) measured in five individuals of *Phascolosoma stephensoni* in the three experimental aquaria.

		Worm 1	Worm 2	Worm 3	Worm 4	Worm 5
Protrusion	4 mm	0.73 ± 0.12	0.87 ± 0.19	0.83 ± 0.19	0.72 ± 0.08	0.65 ± 0.14
	7 mm	1.38 ± 0.10	0.49 ± 0.15	1.42 ± 0.27	1.30 ± 0.41	1.04 ± 0.05
	10 mm	0.42 ± 0.10	0.45 ± 0.15	0.76 ± 0.20	0.22 ± 0.06	0.37 ± 0.06
Retraction	4 mm	0.35 ± 0.26	0.19 ± 0.05	0.29 ± 0.13	0.41 ± 0.35	0.68 ± 0.30
	7 mm	2.07 ± 0.76	1.62 ± 0.26	3.08 ± 0.53	1.10 ± 0.75	1.11 ± 0.43
	10 mm	0.24 ± 0.23	0.58 ± 0.37	0.55 ± 0.54	0.44 ± 0.46	0.21 ± 0.11

Figure 13. Relationship between worm size and retraction speed measured in the three experimental aquaria.

RECONSTRUCTION OF INTERNAL ANATOMY AND STANDARDISED MEASUREMENTS ON ANATOMICAL ELEMENTS INVOLVED IN THE MOVEMENT

For the reconstruction of internal anatomy, microCT technology available at the Hellenic Center for Marine Research was exploited. In particular, Sipuncula (1 in fully expanded and 2 in contracted position) and Phyllodocida specimens (2 *Glycera tridactyla*-1 with everted and 1 with not everted pharynx and 1 *Glycera alba*) were fixed in 4% formalin solution, and they were later subjected to dehydration procedures and stored in 70% ethanol. Subsequently, Sipuncula specimens were stained with 1% iodine dissolved in 96% ethanol modifying the staining protocol presented in Metscher (2009). Phyllodocida specimens were firstly scanned without any contrast agent in order to visualise the jaws and then they were embedded into 0.3% PTA dissolved in 70% ethanol (Metscher 2009) to visualise the pharyngeal anatomy. Micro-CT scans were performed with a SkyScan 1172 micro-tomograph (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) at HCMR. This micro-CT scanner uses a tungsten source and is equipped with an 11 PM CCD camera (4,000 × 2,672 pixels), which can reach a maximal resolution of <0.8 μm/pixel. Sipuncula specimens were scanned at a voltage of 50-60kV and a current of 167-199 μA without filter for a half rotation of 180°. Images were acquired at a pixel size of around 6.89 μm for the specimen in expanded position and 5.52 μm for the specimen in contracted position with a camera binning of 1×1. Phyllodocida specimens were scanned at a voltage of 50-60kV and a current of 167-199 μA without filter for a full rotation of 360°. Images were acquired at a pixel size of around 3.5-4.7 μm with a camera binning of 1×1. Projection images were reconstructed into cross-sections using the SkyScan's NRecon software (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) which employs a modified Feldkamp's back-projection algorithm.

- **Unsegmented Annelida (Sipuncula);**

For Sipuncula specimens, cross section images were loaded into DataViewer v.1.5.6.2 (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) in order to calculate the total body and the four retractor muscles length of the sipuncula specimens. These measurements were repeated 5 times in different slices in order to obtain reliable results. 3D analysis was performed in each micro-CT scan using the software CT Analyzer v.1.18.4.0 (CTAn, Bruker, Kontich, Belgium), in order to calculate the total body and retractor muscles volume. Furthermore, the structure thickness of the retractor muscles was estimated using the CTAn

software through the “sphere-fitting” method (i.e., the average of the diameters of the largest spheres which can be fitted into each point of the muscle) (Hildebrand and Rügsegger, 1997). Based on structure thickness analysis, a color-coded dataset was created in order to visualize the structure thickness distribution throughout the retractor muscles. Volume renderings of the micro-CT scans were created using the CTVox software (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) in order to display the reconstructed and structure thickness images as a 3D object. The retractor muscles segmentation was achieved through the Dragonfly ORS software (v.2020.1.1.809). In the segmented muscles, specific landmarks related to the orientation of the retractor muscles have been added as single points through the Landmark editor software v.3.0.0.6 (Fig. 14).

Figure 14. Single landmarks on the retractor muscles of the Sipuncula.

The measurements regarding the radius of the introvert and the trunk can be found in Table 3. Furthermore, the distance of the ventral and the dorsal retractor muscles from the end of the trunk was calculated (Figs. 16). Specifically, the distance between the ventral retractor muscles and the end of the trunk is longer in the sipuncula specimen in fully expanded position compared to the specimens in contracted position. On the contrary, the distance between the ventral and the dorsal retractor muscles is shorter in the fully expanded specimen compared to the contracted specimens (see also Table 4).

Table 3. Radius ([mm], mean \pm standard deviation) of the introvert and trunk of *Phascolosoma stephensoni* specimens in different body positions.

	Introvert (mm)	Trunk (mm)
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in fully extended position	0.66 \pm 0.1	1.32 \pm 0.05
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in contracted position (specimen 1)	1.58 \pm 0.04	1.66 \pm 0.04
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in contracted position (specimen 2)	1.66 \pm 0.07	1.69 \pm 0.05

Figure 16. Volume rendering of a *Phascolosoma stephensoni* with fully extended body. The distance of ventral retractor muscles (VRM) from the end of the trunk and the distance between the dorsal (DRM) and the ventral (VRM) retractor muscles are indicated. B) Volume rendering of a contracted *Phascolosoma stephensoni* (specimen 1). The distance of ventral retractor muscles (VRM) from the end of the trunk and the distance between the dorsal (DRM) and the ventral (VRM) retractor muscles are indicated. C) Volume rendering of a contracted *Phascolosoma stephensoni* (specimen 2) The distance of ventral retractor muscles (VRM) from the end of the trunk and the distance between the dorsal (DRM) and the ventral (VRM) retractor muscles are indicated.

Table 4. Values of length ([mm], mean \pm standard deviation) and structure thickness ([μ m], mean \pm standard deviation) and the respective volume (mm³) of the *Phascolosoma stephensoni* structures in different body positions.

		Length (mm)	Volume (mm ³)	Structure Thickness (μ m)
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in fully expanded position	Total	32.91 \pm 0.7	49.6	
	VRM1-CP	7.69 \pm 0.43	0.4	152.21 \pm 40.39
	VRM2-CP	7.44 \pm 0.28	0.27	119.61 \pm 51.17
	DRM1-CP	6.38 \pm 0.09	0.13	111.3 \pm 27.56
	DRM2-CP	6.03 \pm 0.31	0.17	100.76 \pm 51.18
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in contracted position (specimen 1)	Total	10.28 \pm 0.09	25.25	
	VRM1-CP	1.31 \pm 0.12	0.41	278.48 \pm 89.67
	VRM2-CP	1.25 \pm 0.14	0.35	249.67 \pm 84.96
	DRM1-CP	1.56 \pm 0.05	0.11	169.88 \pm 52.82
	DRM2-CP	1.92 \pm 0.11	0.29	323.17 \pm 68.7
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in contracted position (specimen 2)	Total	10.47 \pm 0.14	22.41	
	VRM1-CP	1.99 \pm 0.11	0.54	296.21 \pm 84.64
	VRM2-CP	2.07 \pm 0.13	0.41	301.42 \pm 67.51
	DRM1-CP	1.59 \pm 0.12	0.34	232.61 \pm 57.98
	DRM2-CP	1.79 \pm 0.09	0.19	203.95 \pm 49

VRM-ventral retractor muscle; DRM-dorsal retractor muscle; CP-connection point of retractor muscles. These structures correspond in Fig19

The different anatomical structures have been defined with the selection of specific landmarks (Fig. 17). Data derived by the Landmark editor can be found in Table 5.

Figure 17. Surface rendering of the retractor muscles of the *Phascolosoma stephensoni* specimen in A) fully expanded and B) in contracted position. Countour mesh generated by DragonFly ORS software. VRM-ventral retractor muscle; DRM-dorsal retractor muscle; CP- connection point of retractor muscles.

Table 5. XYZ coordinates of the different anatomical structures derived by the Landmark editor. The landmark points are corresponding in Fig. 14 and 17.

	Landmark points	x	Y	z
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in fully expanded position	S0 VRM1	4.2982008e-003	2.8137912e-003	5.5488162e-003
	S1 VRM2	3.9068935e-003	4.6272972e-003	6.3795936e-003
	S2 CP	4.7490140e-003	2.1656957e-003	7.5680423e-003
	S3 DRM1	3.5381261e-003	4.0385188e-003	7.8249145e-003
	S4 DRM2	4.4878740e-003	3.4569514e-003	1.3015676e-002
	S5 Mouth	4.7885515e-003	6.0252389e-003	1.4950405e-002
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in contracted position (specimen 1)	S0 VRM1	4.1905465e-003	3.1807523e-003	8.9196488e-003
	S1 VRM2	1.5284657e-003	4.2615859e-003	8.4004924e-003
	S2 CP	4.1036746e-003	1.9990737e-003	6.8153776e-003
	S3 DRM1	1.8064093e-003	3.9145974e-003	6.2119402e-003
	S4 DRM2	3.2954291e-003	3.5879507e-003	7.6517574e-003
	S5 Mouth	2.7349587e-003	3.6974330e-003	1.4043907e-003
<i>Phascolosoma stephensoni</i> in contracted position (specimen 2)	S0 VRM1	5.4078926e-003	3.0287995e-003	5.7868650e-003
	S1 VRM2	3.0002277e-003	2.1681502e-003	5.5443738e-003
	S2 CP	5.2773622e-003	3.6393730e-003	7.4933595e-003
	S3 DRM1	2.6504910e-003	2.5840558e-003	8.0434596e-003
	S4 DRM2	3.9984570e-003	3.0550659e-003	7.8408541e-003
	S5 Mouth	5.6304689e-003	2.9657891e-003	1.2755597e-002

VRM-ventral retractor muscle; DRM-dorsal retractor muscle; CP-connection point of retractor muscles.

- **Annelida with eversible, armed pharynx (Phyllodocida).**

Regarding the Phyllodocida specimens, the total body length was calculated with an optical stereoscope. The body and proboscis diameter as well as the pharynx length were measured with DataViewer v.1.5.6.2 (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium). For body diameter, length was measured in x (green line) and y (blue line) axes of the cross section image according to Fig. 18. 3D analysis was performed in each micro-CT scan using the software CT Analyzer v.1.18.4.0 (CTAn, Bruker, Kontich, Belgium), in order to calculate the jaws volume and structure thickness. Volume renderings of the micro-CT scans were created using the CTVox software (Bruker, Kontich, Belgium) in order to display the reconstructed and structure thickness images as a 3D object.

The body and pharynx measurements can be found in Table 6. Specifically, the pharynx extends over the 15-20% of the body.

Figure 18. Cross sectional image of the Phyllodocida. Green and blue lines indicate the x and y axes, respectively.

Table 6. Mean values of body and pharyngeal length and body and proboscis diameter (mm, \pm standard deviation) of the *G. alba* and *G. tridactyla* specimens. Body diameter was calculated on x and y axes.

	Body length (mm)	Pharynx length (mm)	Diameter in x axe (mm)	Diameter in y axe (mm)	Diameter of proboscis (mm)
<i>Glycera alba</i> with everted pharynx	23	5,21 \pm 0.18	1.34 \pm 0.04	1.44 \pm 0.08	0.72 \pm 0.07
<i>Glycera tridactyla</i> with everted pharynx	50	7.88 \pm 0.16	1.4 \pm 0.08	1.57 \pm 0.09	0.72 \pm 0.06
<i>Glycera tridactyla</i> with not inverted pharynx	40	5.82 \pm 0.46	1.36 \pm 0.03	1.55 \pm 0.08	0.54 \pm 0.06

CHARACTERIZATION OF AQUARIUM MEDIA

Measurement on gel media in the same aquaria used with worms (see Fig. 9) are being conducted at an Instron testing machine, using the setup depicted in Fig. 19. The main rationale behind these measurements is given by a future extension of the current static model to a dynamic one: to take into account the environmental conditions in which the worm move (i.e., the viscous forces exerted along the worm's body by the fluid-like media in the specific aquaria in which the animal navigates). In addition, this kind of test allows to obtain an indirect measurement of the forces that the worms exert on the environment when moving in these gel-filled aquaria.

Regarding the viscous forces, we derive a constitutive equation that expresses those forces as functions of the speeds of the different body segments.

Here we adopt the resistive force theory, thus assuming that interactions with the medium are local, i.e., different points on the body wall do not influence each other through the action of the gel.

In this context, the equivalent viscosity is then given by

$$\tau(v) = \mu(v) v ,$$

where $\tau = F/A$ is the shear stress on the body wall, i.e., the viscous force per unit area. Here, the coefficient $\mu(v)$ does not correspond to the bulk viscosity of the gel, because of the presence of the

nearby aquarium walls. Therefore, it is an equivalent coefficient, that takes into account the coupling between worm body and aquarium mediated by the gel.

The data acquisition scheme is the following: a metallic rod of diameter close to the one of the worm's introvert is used to penetrate the gel in the aquaria, while being connected to a load cell which records the axial force experienced by it. As for tests on worms, aquaria have 3 thicknesses, namely 4 mm, 7 mm, and 10 mm (see Fig. 9). Penetration is carried out at 4 different speeds: 0.5 mm/s, 1 mm/s, 5 mm/s, 10 mm/s.

Knowing the kinematics of the rod, which is controlled by the Instron Testing machine, we can compute the growing lateral area in contact with the gel, and in turn the shear stress due to viscous forces. Finally, since speed is known, we compute μ during penetration. Once the system reaches its steady state, we select the computed value of μ as a data point to reconstruct its graph as a function of the speed v .

We plan to characterize the equivalent viscosity coefficient in the aquaria for 2 media: an 0.5% agarose gel (already used to record worm movements), and a less elastic, gelatin-based one. Thus, in the future, the model validation will be obtained by the comparison between theoretical model results and experimental data obtained on real worms moving in the same gel media. In addition, this work will allow for an evaluation of the interaction forces with the environment required by worms in order to move within these gels.

Figure 19. Setup for the measure of the equivalent viscosity coefficient. The setup is composed of 6 parts: part 1 is used to interface part 2 with the base frame of the INSTRON machine; part 3 holds the aquarium and interlocks with part 2 with a system of pins, keeping the aquarium at a known position while allowing us to move it by a fixed distance (one pin-to-pin distance). Part 4 and 5 are used to stop lateral movements of the aquarium. Part 6 is used to hold the metallic rod and interface it with moving frame of the machine.

CONCLUSIONS

In order to populate the proposed model, experimental set-ups were developed to acquire data regarding the external geometry, internal anatomy, and morphology of the selected worm species. In particular, geometrical data are acquired through image and video analysis thanks to the set-up reported in Fig. 9. Preliminary results on Sipuncula worms were collected by measuring the axial length of worms and their radius profile, approximated by measuring the radius at 5 points along the body of the worm, both for the fully extended and fully contracted configurations. Regarding the internal anatomy of worms, the characterization can be carried out through CT-scans of the muscles structures of the worm. In particular, the lengths and attachment points of the retractor muscles of Sipuncula specimens were evaluated and reported. Finally, data regarding the equivalent viscosity of selected gels used in the aquaria with worms will be acquired for a dynamic extension of the current model, and for an indirect evaluation of the force exerted by worms on their surroundings when moving in these gels.

Overall, these data also represent a significant step forward in the biomechanical characterization of marine annelida, in particular as regards their motility and shape-morphing, and the role of internal anatomical structures in these processes.

Further development will take into account additional data on the anatomy of sipunculans, as for instance the estimate of the elastic modulus of the body wall or, if possible since challenging, direct measurements of the forces exerted by the worm during the movement. Moreover, the data presented about the Phyllodocida are currently preliminary and restricted to a specific family of the order. Additional comparisons on a higher number of specimens, with different positions of the pharynx, and different species, with different types of jaws, will allow to obtain more precise estimates of the main parameters needed for the final model.

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